

Organizational Leadership through the Massive Transformative Purpose

Received: 13.12.2021
Available online: 30.06.2022

Kiril Dimitrov*

Abstract

Purpose: This study aims at justifying the affiliation of the massive transformative purpose as an important item in the aggregate of the proclaimed corporate culture elements. For this reason the bundle of shades in the meaning for the massive transformative purpose will be explored, bearing in mind the main researcher's interest in outlining the cultural facet of the construct the attributes of which should be further categorized as official and unofficial ones.

Methodology: Literature review and critical analysis of academic publications and blogs of business leaders and consultants in the sphere of the exponential organizations are performed in order to identify important shades in the meaning of the massive transformative purpose. The latter are summarized and categorized as basic nuances and new elaboration streams by the application of the mind-map method. Secondary data analysis and an ethnographic research method are used to identify the cultural facets of the construct, based on its shades of meaning.

Findings: A set of interconnected nuances in the meaning of the massive transformative purpose is grounded through the performed review and critical analysis of books, scientific

articles and blogs. The aforementioned nuances are logically and hierarchically arranged by two useful mind-maps. The outlined cultural facet of the massive transformative purpose is structured into two parts: (1) the first one, containing the core shades of meaning of the construct, and (2) the second one, encompassing the identified new elaboration streams for the construct. Thus, it became possible to propose two new definitions for the massive transformative purpose, embodying the aforementioned parts. In this way, the massive transformative purpose is directly determined as an element of the proclaimed corporate culture, used to formulate and communicate officially the leadership intents of future business development.

Keywords: massive transformative purpose, MTP, corporate culture, proclaimed corporate culture, organizational leadership, strategic management, exponential organizations, startups.

JEL: L21, M14, M13.

Introduction

The last decade seems to be deeply marked by unpredictable and uncontrollable impacts of the VUCA business environment (i.e. volatile, uncertain, complex, ambiguous and even paradoxical) (Gümüşay,

* An associate professor in Industrial business department, University of National and World Economy, Bulgaria

2019; Tulder, Verbeke, Jankowska, 2019; Mack, Khare, Kramer, Burgartz, 2016) and fierce market competition, forcing corporate leaders actively to search for new ways of coping with pending challenges both inside and outside the organizational settings (Kok, van den Heuvel, 2019; George, 2017; Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis, 2014). Since change has been accepted as the only one constant, norm, incessant process, strong impact or revolving leadership challenge in the business world nowadays (Halkias, Santora, Harkiolakis, Thurman, 2020; Comeaux, 2020; Gibbons, 2019a), it is not surprising that new approaches to undertaking proactive change initiatives in contemporary business organizations are needed not only to put an emphasis on reengineering of target business process in companies (Hammer, Champy, 1993; Grover, Kettinger, 1998) or consider to some extent the human side of undertaken organizational change (Lane, 2013; Hiatt, Creasey, 2013; Denison, Hooijberg, Lane, Lief, 2012), but also to extend, redesign and co-create the respective company, its business environment, an entire industry or the society as a whole by means of creative implementation of exponential growth cycle steps, labeled as the 6Ds (digitized, deceptive, disruptive, demonetized, dematerialized and democratized) (Diamandis, Kotler, 2012). These steps may be viewed as organizational enablers (“a chain reaction of technological progression”; Diamandis, Kotler, 2015) to solve the biggest problems, interpreted as the greatest market possibilities by:

- Using acquired entrepreneurship skills to transform human dreams into business reality of sustainable development or at least bring them closer to it,
- Leveraging on the social aspects of innovation with the highest potential impact, and
- Realizing the necessary change initiatives through purpose-driven leadership and smart use of official corporate culture attributes to proclaim such initiatives and engage the respective constituencies with their design and implementation.

Undoubtedly “the more technologically-enabled workplaces become (AI and robotics), paradoxically, the more important the “human” becomes – community, purpose, connection, empathy, relationships, and trust” (Gibbons, 2019b), which brings forth the scientific interest to the cultural aspect of organizational leadership and a possible means of its expression in public and achievement, i.e. *the massive transformative purpose (also applied in the management literature through the abbreviation of MTP)* – a new construct that comes into being. *That is why the aim of the current article* is to justify the affiliation of the massive transformative purpose as an important item in the aggregate of the proclaimed corporate culture elements. For this reason the bundle of shades in the meaning for the massive transformative purpose will be explored, bearing in mind the main researcher’s interest in outlining the cultural facet of the construct which attributes should be further categorized as official and unofficial ones.

Since the MTP represents a construct, still accumulating (and/or rejecting) new nuances in its meaning, it is not surprising that even grammatical instability may be observed in its use, expressed by the availability of diverse labels for it in certain publications (books, articles, blogs) – for example “massively transformative purpose” (Singularity University, 2018a; Diamandis, Kotler, 2015;

Beveridge, 2015; Perez, n.d.), “transformative purpose” (Jain, Schroeter, Branson, 2018), and “mass transformer purpose” (Fernandes, Lucas, Madeira, Cruchinho, 2019, p.448). In some publications the construct of the MTP is barely mentioned (Fernandes, Lucas, Madeira, Cruchinho, 2019; Balanagarajan, Kabaly, 2018; Palao, 2019) while in others it is presented as a peripheral, but integral part of other discussed, surveyed, analyzed topics and issues, related to exponential organizations or exponentially oriented units of already existing companies (Singularity University, 2018a; Diamandis, Kotler, 2015; Pechstein, 2020; Palao, LaPierre, Ismail, Poyatos, Diamandis, 2018) and finally a few publications are entirely devoted to its disclosure (Charania, 2020; Innov8rs team, 2018; Ismail, 2018). The reviewed publications, disclosing some information about the MTP, may be also classified into two groups. The first group presents new scientific results and embodies serious contributions to this field (Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis, 2014; Palao, LaPierre, Ismail, Poyatos, Diamandis, 2018; Palao, Herrera, 2021). The second group of scientific publications communicate and describe either already discovered attributes of the MTP or minor iterations around them, embodying incremental contributions in this field (Balanagarajan, Kabaly, 2018; Innov8rs team, 2018; Mayer, 2016; Beveridge, 2015).

To ensure discipline in the performed reviewing and analysis process, related with the chosen aim of this article, three useful and related constructs should be defined, as follows:

- *Organizational leadership* – associated with the formulation and implementation of the “organizational purpose and design, helping the organization adapt to internal and external change, and building inclusive community inside and outside the organization” (Goethals, Sorenson, Burns, 2004).
- *Exponential growth* – an accelerated expansion of a business organization that doubles every fiscal year for multiple reporting periods, realized within a “new management context” of deliberate leadership intentions to radically solve huge economic and societal problems by means of utilizing breakthrough technologies, establishing cherished culture, implementing social innovations and monitoring a set of specific future-oriented organizational milestones as digitalization, deception, disruption, demonetization, dematerialization, democratization, decentralization and decarbonization (Calvo, 2020; Diamandis, Kotler, 2015; Ismail, Malone, van Geest, Diamandis, 2014; Diamandis, Kotler, 2012).
- *Exponential leadership* – “combining the mindsets, skillsets and networks of futurists, innovators, technologists and humanitarians to create abundant futures” (Singularity university, 2018b).
- *A startup* – “a temporary organization designed to search for a repeatable and scalable business model” (Blank, 2014).
- *Official (proclaimed) corporate culture* – the expressed strategic intentions of leadership in the business organization that acquired civilizational statute by taking the form of written company documents (for example mission, vision, values, principles, purpose, and others) (see Dimitrov, 2017), applied as a “guiding light” in order to solve pending business-related problems.

1. Methodology

Grounding on the MTP as an effective and efficient means of conquering leading positions by business organizations on certain markets and among potential rivals requires the identification of its important shades in the meaning, bearing in mind it is still an emerging construct. That is why research methods as literature review and critical analysis of available publications are used not only within the traditional category of academic publications – i.e. monographies and articles, but also within a selected group of blogs, maintained by business or opinion leaders and consultants, demonstrating their professional interests in the field of exponential organizations, and especially the sub-sphere of the MTP. It should be noted that books and scientific articles, just mentioning or deeper related to the topic of the MTP in academic databases are few (** 2021d; ** 2021e; ** 2021f; ** 2021g; ** 2021h; ** 2021i; ** 2021j). The aforementioned blogs were found through the application of highly ranked internet search engines for 2021 (Chris, 2021). Thus, the two main sources of forming and elaborating of the MTP construct seem to be simultaneously used, i.e. the experience of managers/ consultants in real leading business organizations and the proposed novel scientific ideas, concepts, principles, theories, methodologies, etc. by researchers and consultants. In fact this is the way of accumulating knowledge for management as a science.

Furthermore, the mind-map method is applied to summarize and categorize the identified shades in the meaning of the MTP as basic nuances and new elaboration streams of the aforementioned construct (Buzan, 2018; Kachel, Jennings, 2020; Wheeldon, Ahlberg, 2019; Wheeldon, Åhlberg, 2012; Wheeldon,

Faubert, 2009; Tattersall, Watts, Vernon, 2007). Next, the cultural facets of the MTP are deliberately identified through assessment of the already identified aggregate of shades and streams, i.e. secondary data analysis (Janicijevic, 2011) and ethnographic research method (Schein, 1990) are applied. Finally, the attention is oriented to distinguishing these cultural attributes of the MTP that may be semantically related to Schein's second level of organizational culture (i.e. the proclaimed corporate culture or official culture) (Schein, Schein, 2017; Schein, 1990; Dimitrov, 2017). Finally two useful definitions for the construct of the MTP are proposed, introducing the perspective of the proclaimed corporate culture in its existence – the first one, based on the MTP core, and the second one, based on the MTP new elaboration streams. In this way the construct is positioned as an effective and efficient trigger of cherished cultural change, aligned with an adopted company strategy of exponential growth in order to conquer an organizational leadership position on the global or target market.

2. The emergence of the MTP

The construct of the MTP is very succinctly formulated as “the higher, aspirational purpose of the organization” by Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis (2014, p.48). It may be viewed as a set of sincerely, confidently and officially expressed shared high generalized corporate aspirations “to accomplish near-miracles”, intended to win the “hearts and minds - imaginations and ambitions” of all company stakeholders, especially those outside the boundaries of the entity (Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis, 2014, p.48). Those corporate aspirations are broadly formulated without technological specificity. The MTP is considered more as a passion

Articles

to be pursued by the company, rather than a business decision to be implemented by leaders and employees. In fact this construct emerges as a result from a larger research project, conducted by the aforementioned team of authors, and targeted to explore peculiarities in the performance of the top one hundred fastest growing startups worldwide within the time interval of 2008-2014 (Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis, 2014).

Furthermore, three of the aforementioned authors (i.e. Salim Ismail, Yuri van Geest and Peter Diamandis) constitute a part of a greater team of prominent figures in the fields of entrepreneurship, management of innovations and business consulting, including Ray Kurzweil, Robert Richards, Michael Simpson, Susan Fonseca and others who established the Singularity University in 2007 to educate, research and consult people and companies about “the exponential pace of change” (Singularity University, 2021). This is the reason why the existence of strong semantic closeness between ideas, principles,

frameworks, etc., presented in the book by Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis (2014) may be assumed and the information from some free-access educational materials, found on the website of the Singularity University, especially oriented to the core in the narrow sub-sphere of the MTP. This group of scientific publications may be viewed as the base of the elaboration for this emerging construct. Thus, it seems logical that the proposed definition of this emerging construct is chosen to be formulated in a succinct way, while the accumulating nuances in its meaning are identified and disclosed predominantly through the lens of diverse management theories and approaches (traditional and modern), as follows: the system approach, strategic management process, concrete examples, problem approach, important characteristics, results (benefits) from the construct’s implementation, requirements to its use, focus and levels of its realization and decision-making theory (table 1).

Table 1: The management theories and approaches, applied in outlining key nuances in the meaning of the MTP

Approaches	Key nuances in the meaning of the construct
<i>System approach</i>	The basic characteristic for being (or becoming) an exponential organization within a set of eleven characteristics (e.g. “common traits”), accelerating its market performance in comparison to the competitors.
<i>Strategic management process</i>	It embodies the junction among high quality daring business dreaming by corporate leaders, radical transformation and rapid (coherent, exponential) growth, achieved by creative strategy design, implementation and many iterations.
<i>Examples</i>	MTP, developed by exponential organizations as TED, Google, X Prize Foundation, Quirky and Singularity University.
<i>Problem approach</i>	Key questions: “Why do this work?” and “Why does the organization exist?” Other questions (Pursuing your passion): “What makes you come alive and go do it?”, “What do I really care about?”, “What am I meant to do?”, “What would I do if I could never fail?” and “What would I do if I received a billion dollars today?”

Approaches	Key nuances in the meaning of the construct	
<i>Important characteristics</i>	(a) Shortness (b) Simplicity (c) Uniqueness (d) A source of strong cultural impact on the company and around it (e) A landmark for team members in the external impact of their contributions (deliverables) and needed agility-and-learning oriented collaborations (f) Appropriate only for “first movers” (g) Wide focused (h) High emotionality (hearts, minds, passion) (i) Credibility, supporting confidence in daily work (j) A guide to people (insiders & outsiders) (k) A guide to scale process (l) Technology-neutral	(m) Strong (n) Difficult for replication (o) Great potential force of attraction to the company and retention in it for diverse stakeholders as talent, customers, developers, startups, hackers, NGOs, governments, suppliers, partners, etc. (p) A stabilizing force for the business organizations during periods of random growth (q) Oriented outside the narrow view of company profit margins (r) It “sets the tone” of dominating company culture (s) Enabler of agility and learning environment
<i>Results (benefits) from its use</i>	A cultural movement in the company and for its constituencies. Achievement of competitive (economic) advantage. A competitive edge. (Attract and retain the best talent, creation of communities, organizational depoliticization). Shifting the organizational focus from internal politics to external impact. High focused leadership in times of rapid (exponential) growth or severe stress.	
<i>Requirements to its use</i>	Constant action of all participators is required. Everyone involved is required to walk the talk.	
<i>Focus & levels of realization</i>	Radical (large-scale) transformation of an organizational unit, entire organization (not only a company), industry, community, social movement, the whole planet etc. “Solving a massive global problem”.	
<i>Decision-making theory</i>	Organizational leaders have to make a strategic choice – “Join or create a MTP?”. In early development stages many companies prefer joining an existing community that shares an existing MTP to creating their own specific (unique) ones.	

Sources: Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis (2014); Berman (2016a); Singularity university (2019, 2018a); Berman (2016b); SMExO community (n.d.); Ismail (2018).

Other important nuances in the semantic bundle of the MTP are outlined by means of its deliberate comparisons with some close constructs, modern and post-modern management theories (table 2) (Ismail, Malone, van Geest, Diamandis, 2014).

Table 2: MTP in comparison with some close constructs, modern and post-modern management theories

Compared pairs of constructs	Descriptions
<i>MTP & mission</i>	MTP is more inspirational, aspirational and transformative in comparison to the company mission.
<i>MTP & aspirational brands</i>	There may exist some overlap between their meanings.
<i>MTP & the theory of the social enterprise</i>	There may exist some overlap between their meanings.

Compared pairs of constructs	Descriptions
<i>MTP in small markets...</i>	MTP accepts the form of organizational mantra.
<i>MTP & shareholder theory...</i>	MTP may become a component of the stock portfolio strategies, designed and implemented by potential or current shareholders.
<i>MTP & stakeholder theory...</i>	MTP represents a useful means of nurturing the community of the company, defined as “an extension” of the entity itself.
<i>MTP in the process of the establishment of cherished culture...</i>	MTP is the result from the second phase in the establishment of cherished culture, occurring after the emergence of shared informal culture by the founders (the first phase), and before its transposition at team and organizational levels due to the impact of factors as the penetration of new people in the organization and the applied social technologies (the third phase).

Source: Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis (2014).

The outlined core of nuances in the meaning of the MTP may be logically arranged as a set by a useful mind-map (see figure 1), categorizing the items as nuances, subordinated facets and especially specific culture-related facets. On this basis it may be concluded that the cultural facet is embedded in the MTP through:

- Some of its essential characteristics.
- Its intrinsic connectivity with the process of establishment of a cherished culture in a target entity that is usually undertaken by its founders and later on, if the respective startup is transformed into a stable company – by its formal and informal leadership. Since it becomes evident that an MTP takes the form of a written company document that has acquired a civilizational statute, it may be logically assigned to the elements of the proclaimed corporate culture.
- MTP’s core meaning is positioned to be designed and implemented by both established big corporations and small startups, enabled to pursue growth accelerations not only on global markets, but also on numerous local markets.
- On small markets the meaning of an MTP converges with the meaning, embedded in the construct of organizational mantra (Dimitrov, 2017).
- Positive results from its application, i.e. deliberate generation and realization of cherished cultural influence to higher rank cultural levels beyond the boundaries of the organizational setting (Dimitrov, 2012).
- Its role as a catalyzer of the “culture-strategy” relationship in the business organization (Dimitrov, 2016), disclosed as pursued competitive advantage or gained competitive edge.
- Its direct comparison with just two elements in the aggregate of official corporate culture documents – mission and organizational mantra, incarnating the first leadership endeavor in conducting the strategic management process in business organizations.

Figure 1: The core nuances in the meaning of the MTP

3. New streams in elaborating the meaning of the MTP

The forming streams, accumulating new nuances to the already presented and analyzed core meaning of the MTP, are arranged in certain order, determined by the simultaneous use of two criteria, as follows:

- *The respective years of publication for the research (books, articles, blogs), presenting significant contributions to this sub-sphere, and*
- *Deliberate categorization of these publications, taking into account the sharpness and urgency of the specific needs by diverse social actors for the timely operationalization of the aforementioned construct.*

An enlarged and a bit renewed team of researchers, consultants and entrepreneurs (Palao, LaPierre, Ismail, Poyatos and Diamandis, 2018) has also made great contributions, regarding the elaboration of the MTP by creating, trialing and developing a specific ExO (i.e. the exponential organization) Sprint approach in order to manage the innovation interventions in the contemporary business organizations through organizing a series of repeatable workshops and meetings, oriented to leveraging the creativity of diverse constituencies, pursuing accelerated growth and implementing deep changes in and outside the respective organizational setting, i.e. at organizational, industrial and societal level. *Thus, the implementation of the exponential organization model comes into being as a research stream for exploring the essence of*

the MTP, comprised by six perspectives in its bundle. The contributions of Palao, LaPierre, Ismail, Poyatos and Diamandis (2018) are worth mentioning within the aforementioned stream who succeed in adding two new perspectives to deliberate disclosure of important nuances in the meaning of MTP. First, the MTP is positioned as an important sub-component from the second phase “execute” (sub-phase “discover”, 1-4th week and sub-phase “disrupt”, 5th week) of conducted specific ExO sprint for a target company. Here, the MTP is intended to receive its realizations in two alternative “streams”, categorized by the level

of accepted initiative-related risks (Palao, LaPierre, Ismail, Poyatos and Diamandis, 2018), as follows (see table 3):

- “Edge Stream”, defined as a means for the creation of next-generation global companies, capable of leading an existing or new industry, and
- “Core Stream”, defined as a means for adaptation of an “existing organization to external industry disruption by embracing the adoption of new technologies and organizational techniques” under the conditions of a company’s current business model.

Table 3: The MTP as an important sub-component in an ExO sprint for a target company

Streams of ExO sprint	Steps of ExO sprint	Tasks in which the MTP is applied...
(1)	(2)	(3)
The Edge Stream	Ideate (week 2)	Task 1: Formulation of MTPs - Searching for answers to the question “why the company wants to exist in this world”. - Describing desired features of the world in a case the company attains success in its initiatives. - A set of MTPs has to be initially formulated by the participants. Task 2: Determination of problem/solution pairs for each of the generated MTPs: - Minimum ten pairs of problems/solutions are required. - One MTP may be related to one or more problem/solution pairs. - Each problem/solution pair represents an ExO Edge Initiative
	Select (week 4)	Task 1: - The MTP serves as one of a set of three appraisal criteria for the selection of the four most promising ideas. - The MTP criterion is measured by indicators as its massiveness, strength of inspiration, and received results from the conducted experiments. Task 4: - The MTP is used as an item for the conducted extended elevator pitch for each ExO Edge Initiative.

Streams of ExO sprint	Steps of ExO sprint	Tasks in which the MTP is applied...
(1)	(2)	(3)
<i>The Core Stream</i>	<i>Ideate (week 2)</i>	Task 1: - The formulation of a MTP is performed in congruence with other already existing proclaimed corporate culture documents as company vision and mission. Task 2: - The proposed MTP should be supported by determination of multiple external disruption/internal reaction pairs. - The identified and analyzed external disruptions should be relevant to the company and chosen MTP. - Internal organizational reactions should be designed in order to adapt to or take advantage of external disruption. - Each disruption/reaction pair represents an ExO Core Initiative.
	<i>Select (week 4)</i>	Task 3: - The MTP is positioned as an item of the elevator pitch.
	<i>Disrupt (week 5)</i>	Task 4: - The MTP incarnates the adequate and timely decision of the leadership team who either choose one of the already proposed MTPs or define their own.

Source: Palao, LaPierre, Ismail, Poyatos and Diamandis (2018).

Second, the MTP is defined as an official corporate culture document, designed and approved by senior management in collaboration with teams of key employees and representatives of other stakeholders. It is created to develop further the ideas, strivings and stances, proclaimed in existing company vision and mission.

Third, the time perspective to defining a corporate MTP may also be identified, based on a clearly defined interval. Nevertheless the aforementioned five week period, needed for the conduct of the entire MTP formulation process (Palao, LaPierre, Ismail, Poyatos and Diamandis, 2018), the reality may also be quite different – from a week to almost a year (Innov8rs team, 2018).

The fourth perspective outlines the MTP as an element in the framework of hybrid thinking that needs to be pursued in a rapid way by the company through leveraging the abundance, generated by information and

technology advancement, and intertwined disruptions. It emerges as a contemporary crisis management response or proactive activity, undertaken by organizational leadership. Thus, the MTP may be defined as a means of “building a circular economy”, characterized by profitability, justice (fairness) and value-creation (Pechstein, 2020). In fact MTP may be directly associated with at least two cutting-edge management (methods) interventions within the innovation and transformation framework of hybrid thinking as “vision” and “agility” as leadership reactions and/or proactive actions to the unpredictable and frequently unfavorable impacts of the VUCA business environment. In its turn, Hybrid thinking consists in a deliberate and intensive application of modern techniques as Biomimicry (innovation inspired by nature), Design thinking, Agile and Exponential organizations, integrated under the management and leadership

theories of Neuroscience, Systems Thinking and Complex Adaptive Systems, intended to drive numerous necessary behavioral and organizational changes (Pechstein, 2020).

*The fifth perspective reveals the MTP as a cultural attribute, serving as a prerequisite for the establishment or joining of certain infrastructure, meant to ensure and sustain the efficient and effective interaction and alignment among necessary components inside and outside the contemporary exponential organizational setting (Singularity university, 2019). The list of these components includes: a newly established company to solve a chosen big problem; a group of identified entrepreneurial organizations already engaged in this field; the creation of an incentive scheme for specialists and entities to put in efforts and achieve results in the solution of the problem (a version of an XPRIZE or a HeroX) (***, 2021b; ***, 2021c); a group of identified other constituencies, contributing in specific ways to the respective cause; a new electronic platform, intended to bind together talent and resources in order to solve the problem; wide attraction of other investors to financing the potential solutions of the chosen problem by establishing a fund.*

The sixth perspective uncovers the MTP as a key element in “Purpose Launchpad” – a proposed “meta-methodology with which people can evolve early stage ideas into purpose-driven, sustainable and eventually exponential organizations that will make the greatest possible impact” (Palao, 2020, p.4). It is considered that the potential success of such an organizational initiative depends on a mandatory condition – the evolutionary achievement of a stable transition in the mindset of founders, employees and other key constituencies who are expected to occupy the role of “explorers”, searching for and

discovering “the right path to create a new organization, business, product or service” with “a positive impact” on this world. In this methodology “purpose” represents the first item in a set of key interconnected areas (Purpose Launchpad Axes) and justifies the reason for the existence of the respective deep change initiative. In this case the MTP is positioned as the appropriate framework within the aforementioned key area. Furthermore, the process of its formulation is supported by bringing into use of a new, specific tool – the MTP canvas, encompassing nine elements (“steps”) that may be applied at both an organizational and individual level (Palao, Herrera, 2021; Charania, 2020).

The orientation to high-quality in the MTP design process may also be identified as a forming stream, outlining two new perspectives in the bundle of complementary shades of meaning that constitute the essence of the aforementioned construct. Actually, the high-quality of the MTP design process may be achieved, maintained and/ or increased by disseminating this research-based information in two forms, as follows:

- Employee training, management and stakeholder development programs, planned and/ or implemented in existing companies or recently created startups (Palao, LaPierre, Ismail, Poyatos and Diamandis, 2018), and
- University modules in master of economy courses as an educational and qualification degree for students, soon expected to enter the contemporary labor market or already partially employed (Palao, 2019).

All the constituencies in the design and implementation process of the MTP should be persuaded that this is the right “way to perceive, think, and feel” (Schein, Schein, 2017) in relation to the issue of pursuing 10x

business growth within the VUCA business environment, thus establishing and stabilizing a cherished dominating organizational and community culture, oriented to continuous and radical innovating (Palao, n.d.). *Thus, the new training and development perspective to clarifying the meaning of the MTP (the first perspective) emerges in its two versions – the corporate training and the academic lecturing and seminars.*

The university modules, adopting the ExO sprint approach, require withdrawal of the traditionally applied in the educational process case-study methods, presenting diverse stories of companies from the past that students have to analyze, using conventional frameworks and instruments (business plans, SWOT analysis, etc.). The emphasis should be concentrated on the theory, embedded in lectures on the management of the exponential business organizations, use of selected new types of innovation methodologies (MTP, Design thinking, Customer development, Lean startup, Exponential transformation, Business model generation, Purpose Launchpad, Agile frameworks, etc.), especially formulation of organizational and individual purpose, and ExO sprint approach seminars where students are assigned to teams whose members accept the role of emulating the work tasks they would perform for a specific company while actively contributing to the creation of its future exponentially growing version and a better world (Palao, 2019; Palao, 2020). Thus, it seems that the MTP formulation process

incites the participants to assess whether, to what extent and in what way they utilize their entrepreneurial skills in the pursuit of their business dream, i.e. the world that they themselves “want to create” (Trodden, n.d.).

According to Palao (2020, p.8), the high-quality formulation of MTP (iterations, preliminary evaluations, appraisal of the potential impact) requires not only disclosure of an extended bundle of core official corporate culture documents, their succinct semantic description and differentiation, especially from the MTP, but also the establishment of a certain hierarchy among at least some of the aforementioned constructs, suitable for the exponential organizations or units. *Thus, the second perspective of disclosing the essence of MTP within this stream comes into existence, i.e. to explain what is not an MTP by its comparing to (and differentiating from) other official corporate culture attributes that have acquired civilizational status in the form of written company documents.* The presented information about the extended bundle of official culture attributes relies on several identified publications whose authors apply such research approach (table 4). The MTP is outlined here through two proposed definitions, as follows (Palao, Lapierre, Ismail, 2019):

- The great/ deep change the organizational leaders want to achieve.
- A means that “allows the organization to modify its approach, and even pivot, over time.”

Table 4: The extended bundle of official culture attributes, suitable for the exponential organizations or units

Cultural attribute	Description	Sources	Ranked to the MTP
<i>a vision (statement)</i>	It describes what the company is and what senior managers want it to become in the future.	Palao (2020); Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019)	Low rank
<i>a mission (statement)</i>	- How the organizational leaders will make their vision become reality. (1) - In what way the organization meets its purpose (not MTP)	(1) - Palao (2020) (2) - Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019); Berman (2016b)	Low rank
<i>a (massive transformative) purpose</i>	The reason why the company exists. A means of envisioning a better world and raising the potential organizational impact to a higher level. A bridge between the biggest challenges and the best business opportunities.	Palao (2020)	High rank
<i>values</i>	The way the personnel members operate together as an organization.	Palao (2020)	Not ranked
<i>a moonshot</i>	An ambitious goal to be reached within the next 5-10 years.	Palao (2020)	Not ranked
<i>About/ for us</i>	Official information only about the company.	Ismail (2018).	Not ranked
<i>a marketing slogan (tagline)</i>	It promotes a product or service (not MTP). It may be geared to two stakeholders: (a) the customers (the applied statements often include “you”), and (b) the company (the applied statements often include “us” or “we”)	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019); Singularity university (2018)	Not ranked
<i>big goal; big hairy audacious goal</i>	A purpose has to drive a chosen MTP, so that a transformative impact is created.	Berman (2016b)	Not ranked

The mingling (matching, simultaneous application) of two approaches to exploring the essence of MTP constitutes the third modern and a bit complicated research stream, demonstrating high potential to add new shades in the construct’s meaning (Palao, Lapierre, Ismail, 2019). It consists of two perspectives. Within the first perspective Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019) combine identified characteristics of MTP (descriptive

approach) with respective questions (i.e. the problem approach), the deliberate answers to which may confirm the achievement, any level of possession or absence of certain characteristic (table 5). It seems that the answers for each posed question are applied as an adequate analysis and measure of the respective characteristic, increasing the quality level of the overall MTP design and implementation process.

Table 5: Matching two approaches to describing the essence of MTP

MTP characteristics	Posed problem
<i>Purposeful</i>	What do you want to achieve?
<i>Descriptive of the world</i>	What would the world look like once the MTP has been achieved?
<i>Succinct</i>	Is it short, simple, and clear, need explanation?
<i>Connected to abundance</i>	How is a new abundance created or an existing abundance drawn upon?

Articles

MTP characteristics	Posed problem
<i>Massive</i>	Is it global in scope, or does it have the potential to be?
<i>Inspiring</i>	If you shared your MTP with a stranger, would it inspire him or her to get involved?
<i>Highly aspirational</i>	Is the MTP grand and bold? Does it lie just beyond what seems to be possible to achieve?
<i>Transformative</i>	How would the world be changed for the better if the MTP were achieved?
<i>Passionate</i>	Does the MTP convey your passion?
<i>Positive</i>	How does everyone win?

Source: Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).

The *second perspective* combines the project management principles (by creating a checklist) and the problem approach (by posing important questions) in the outlining of key nuances for the MTP (table 6).

Table 6: Design of MTP checklist

Type of check	Searching for answers to the questions...	Literature sources
Quick check	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is it massive? 2. Is it transformative? 3. Is it a true purpose? (purposeful) 	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019); Ismail, Malone, van Geest, Diamandis (2014).
Detailed check	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "Is it simple, clear and easy to understand?" 2. "Is it strong, bold and challenging?" 3. "Does it reflect an important and meaningful purpose?" 4. "Will it change the world for the better?" 5. Is it unique?" 6. "Does it define why our organization exists?" 7. "Does it reflect the passions of our company's leadership?" 8. "Is it well communicated and understood throughout our organization?" 9. "Does it draw a community and give it something to rally around?" 10. "Does it seem almost impossible to fully achieve, yet imperative enough that we want to try?" 	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
Check, performed only by managers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "What do we stand for?" 2. "How bold is this stance?" 3. "Are we capturing the hearts, minds, imaginations and ambitions of those inside and outside the business?" 4. "How committed to this are we?" 5. "What significant problem needs a champion?" 6. "So what do you stand for?" 	Beveridge (2015).

The deliberate reliance on project management principles in MTP's design and implementation processes and tasks strengthens the perceptions of company leaders, employees and other constituencies, regarding the high probability of their potential successful and timely completions, including the creation of desired deliverables. This perspective in the exploration of MTP essence is not entirely new, because its

Articles

“quick check” version was proposed earlier by Ismail, Malone, van Geest, Diamandis (2014) (i.e. key questions). The aforementioned publication also contains an earlier version of the so called “detailed check” that was predominantly oriented to the process of “pursuing your passion” (i.e. other questions), i.e. at individual, team or organizational levels (e.g. founders, small teams) in exponential organizations (Ismail, Malone, van Geest, Diamandis, 2014) (see table 1).

Putting an emphasis on examples of real MTPs, belonging to companies whose senior leaders pursue exponential growth, achieve current great successes and/or maintain sustainable high results from their activities, seems to be considerably increased in the publication by Palao, Lapierre and Ismail (2019) in comparison to the initial publication in the field of exponential organizations by Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis (2014) (table 7). This situation emerged due to the accumulation of successful cases from the consulting experiences of the respective researchers, consultants, entrepreneurs and business gurus (not only Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis, 2014; Palao, Lapierre,

Ismail, 2019). That is why now it may be concluded *that providing examples of MTPs represents a comparatively stable stream in disclosing important shades in the meaning for the aforementioned construct*, bringing to its greater popularity and higher trust in it as a driver of exponential business growth among constituencies. It should be mentioned that most of the provided examples of MTPs belong to existing big or even global business organizations or their entities or units, recently established by their senior management, provided higher level of independence from the other groupings in the respective organizational structures of management and almost no collaborations among them. Some MTPs embed examples for initiated projects and/or undertaken initiatives, led, controlled or at least sponsored by prominent entrepreneurs, companies or movements (Ismail, 2018). Although it is officially stated that the MTPs also matter to small and medium sized business (SMExO community, n.d.), such examples are few and even missing in the majority of the reviewed publications (see table 7).

Table 7: The enriched list of exemplary companies, applying specific MTPs

Exemplary companies, oriented to exponential growth & their specific MTPs	Literature sources
<i>TED</i> - “Ideas worth spreading.”	Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis (2014) (chapter 3); Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019); Singularity university (2019), Ismail (2018).
<i>Google</i> - “Organize the world’s information.”	Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis (2014) (chapter 3); Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019); Singularity university (2019); Ismail (2018).
<i>X Prize Foundation</i> - “Bring about radical breakthroughs for the benefit of humanity.”	Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis (2014) (chapter 3); Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019); Singularity university (2019); Ismail (2018).
<i>Quirky</i> - “Make invention accessible.”	Ismail, Malone, van Geest and Diamandis (2014) (chapter 3); Ismail (2018).

Articles

Exemplary companies, oriented to exponential growth & their specific MTPs	Literature sources
<i>Virgin Galactic</i> – “Democratizing access to space for the benefit of life to earth”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Singularity University</i> – (1) “Positively impact one billion people”; (2) “Building an Abundant Future Together.”	(1) Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019). (2) Singularity university (n.d.); Ismail (2018).
<i>Terepac</i> – “Giving voice to the world”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Waze</i> – “Outsmarting traffic, together”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Phillips</i> – “Make the world healthier”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Swarovski</i> – “Add sparkle to people’s everyday lives”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>World Top 20 Project</i> – “Educate every child on the planet”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019); Ismail (2018).
<i>Infinitum Humanitarian Systems</i> – “Creating Safer Futures”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Zendrive</i> – “Safer drivers, safer roads”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>GitHub</i> – “Social coding”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Virgin Group</i> – “Changing business for good”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Dove</i> – “Help the next generation of women realize their full potential”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Starbucks</i> – “Inspire and nurture the human spirit”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Tesla</i> – (1) “Accelerate the world’s transition to sustainable energy”; (2) “Accelerate the transition to sustainable transportation”	- Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019) for (1). On the corporate website statement (1) is labeled as Tesla’s mission (***, 2021a). There is no provided information for the MTP on Tesla’s website. - Innov8rs team (2018); Singularity university (2019) for (2).
<i>Unilever</i> – “Make sustainable living commonplace”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Nike</i> – “Bring inspiration and innovation to every athlete in the world”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Ikea</i> – “Create a better everyday life for people”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Chipotle</i> – “Food with integrity”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Spotify</i> – “Music for everyone”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Microsoft</i> – “Help individuals and businesses realize their full potential”	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019).
<i>Boston Children’s Hospital</i> – “Until Every Child is Well”	Innov8rs team (2018); Kinkade (2018); Ismail (2018).
<i>Netflix</i> – “To change the way people watch movies and television”	Innov8rs team (2018).
<i>Solar City</i> – “Pioneering the Future of Energy”	Innov8rs team (2018).
<i>Space-X</i> – “Humans must become an multi-planetary species”	Innov8rs team (2018).
<i>Magellan Health</i> – “Leading humanity to healthy, vibrant lives.”	Nwatarali (2021).
<i>Uber</i> – “The best way to get wherever you’re going”	Kinkade (2018).

Exemplary companies, oriented to exponential growth & their specific MTPs	Literature sources
<i>Coca-Cola</i> – “Refresh the world and inspire moments of optimism”	Kinkade (2018).
<i>Apple</i> – “Think different”	Peppler (2019).
<i>LightSail Education</i> – “Turning students into readers”	Ismail (2018).
<i>Business Interviews .com</i> – “We tell your story to the world”	Ismail (2018).
<i>St. Margaret’s school for girls</i> – “This is school where girls who want to change the world become women who do”	Ismail (2018).
<i>INTERProteccion ExO project</i> – “Simply solving humanity’s risks”	Ismail (2018).
<i>Angels of impact</i> – “Women creating an inclusive and prosperous world for all”	Ismail (2018).
<i>Xprize</i> – “To build a bridge to abundance for all”	Ismail (2018).
<i>Care Pay</i> – “Connect people to quality healthcare”	Ismail (2018).
<i>Elon Musk’s initiative of SolarCity</i> – “Pioneering the future of energy”	Ismail (2018).
<i>Elon Musk’s initiative of Tesla</i> - “Pioneering the future of automobiles”	Ismail (2018).
<i>Elon Musk’s initiative of SpaceX</i> - “Pioneering the future of space travel”	Ismail (2018).
<i>Best Friends Animal Rescue</i> – “Save them All”	Jeffery (2019).
<i>Amazon</i> – “To be earth’s most customer-centric company; to build a place where people can come to find and discover anything they might want to buy online”	Trodden (n.d.)
<i>NASA</i> – “We reach for new heights and reveal the unknown for the benefit of humankind”	Trodden (n.d.)
<i>SquareSpace</i> – “Make beautiful products to help people with creative ideas succeed”	Trodden (n.d.)

A useful stream in marking out an important shade in the meaning of MTP is to propose appropriate team/ individual creativity stimulating and ideation tools (schemes, instruments, sets of steps), and specific milestones, ensuring the high quality formulation of the aforementioned construct (table 8). Some of the tools (schemes, instruments and exercises) comprise sets of questions that should be answered based on discussions by respective participants (teams) in certain MTP formulation events,

characterized by necessary iterations of certain phases. While minority of these tools (instruments) comprise steps, some (all) of them supported by specific techniques (Peppler, 2019; Palao, Lapierre, Ismail, 2019; Palao, Herrera, 2021). In this group some tools are oriented to individuals, e.g. founders of the recently created startups or other organizational contributors who are expected to reach a consensus around a final version of an MTP.

Table 8: Specific tools, schemes, instruments, steps and recommended milestones to craft an MTP

Tools, schemes, instruments, steps & milestones to craft an MTP	Key Content	Sources
<i>A Why – How – What tool</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Why does an organization exist? - define the problem space (MTP is found during this stage) 2. How will the organization address the need or opportunity? (solve the problem; imagine the transformation) 3. What will the organization deliver? (Brainstorm ideas) 	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019)
<i>A Why – How – What tool – Ismail's version</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Why does the organization exist? 2. How will the organization solve it? 3. What will be the global impact? (orientation to the largest possible audience) 	Ismail (2018)
<i>Growth institute's MTP tool</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Drafting of an MTP (teamwork): (1.1.) "What do we really care about? Why?" (1.2.) "What is our company's purpose on this earth (and beyond)?" (1.3.) "What does the world hunger for? Why?" (1.4.) "What would we do if we could never fail? Why?" (1.5.) "What would we do if we received a billion dollars today? Why?" 2. Testing a draft of an MTP: (2.1.) Appraising certain qualities of an MTP (a provided list, inclusion, removal) (2.2.) Quick Test - The MTP Cocktail Party ("Will your MTP cause the right people to "lean in"?", "What do you do?") 	Growth institute (n.d.)
<i>A five WHYs tool - Brainstorming technique - Participating stakeholders: personnel members (from different organizational spheres and hierarchical levels), clients and partners.</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Why does the organization exist? 2. Why are we doing this? (for chosen items during the previous phase) - repeated three times 3. Going back to the previous round of answers, if the upper limit of abstractness in the formulation process is reached, because it cannot be utilized, i.e. "To save the world". - searching for similar ideas and common themes 	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019)
<i>The scheme of the two focus areas to identify an MTP by Peter Diamandis</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (who): "What community (potential group) do you want to create a lasting positive impact for?" 2. (what): What problem do you want to take on and solve? Related assessment questions: (2.1.) If at the end of your life you had made a significant dent in this area, how proud would you feel? (2.2.) Given the resources you have today, what level of impact could you make in the next three years if you solved this problem? (2.3.) Given the resources you expect to have in 10 years, what level of impact could you make in a 3-year period? (2.4.) How well do I understand the problem? (2.5.) How emotionally charged (excited or riled up) am I about this? (2.6.) Will this problem get solved with or without you involved? 3. Performing deep research: (3.1.) Proceed with your own literature research. (3.2.) Communicate with leading experts in the field. (3.3.) Attempt to kill the idea (obstacles, risks, weaknesses, reasons why it will not work well). 	Berman (2016b); Singularity university (2019)

Tools, schemes, instruments, steps & milestones to craft an MTP	Key Content	Sources
<i>An Open Discussion tool</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is the change you want to see in the world? 2. How will this change positively impact the society? 3. What gets you out of bed every morning? 4. For what greater cause would you gladly volunteer time? 	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019)
<i>A storytelling tool</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the narrative behind what inspires your organization? - each participant should compose his narrative (three paragraphs, one page) 	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019)
<i>A powerful exercise to define MTP as a purpose-driven leader</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the things that attract your curiosity (deliverable: a list of at least 25 items) 2. Mapping the potential intersections between/ among some of these curiosities (more curiosities in one intersection = a passion) 3. Making a list of problems that intensify your sensitivity and you would love to solve (preferred problems: 10-15 problems). 4. Identify the potential intersections between the preferred problems and your passions. <p>Each one of the intersections (step 4) represents a version of a potential MTP.</p>	Perez (n.d.)
<i>SMExO community – MTPs for small & medium-sized enterprises</i>	<p>Two levels of realization (individual & organizational).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Searching for an MTP (10 minutes): (1.1.) “When you were a child, what did you want to be? Before your parents, teachers, or friends told you what you should be, what is it that gave you the most joy?” (1.2.) “If someone gave you a billion dollars and told you to use it to do something that would change the world, what would you do with it?” (three ideas) (1.3.) “Who do you want to be a hero to?” (1.4.) “Unrestricted, what is it today that gives you joy? If you had a month off to go and learn about anything, what would be three things that you would do?” 2. Drafting a few variations of an MTP (final choice, possibilities for many updates) 	SMExO community (n.d.)
<i>Individual business MTPs – an instrument, based on a Japanese concept</i>	<p>Five interconnected and partially overlapping spheres:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What you love (passion + mission + delight and fullness, but no wealth) 2. What the world needs (mission + vocation + excitement and complacency, but sense of uncertainty) 3. What you can be paid for (profession + vocation + comfortable, but feeling of emptiness) 4. What you are good at (passion + profession + satisfaction, but feeling of uselessness) 5. IKIGAI (a reason to exist/ live) = MTP 	Peppler (2019)
<i>The MTP canvas</i>	<p>It encompasses nine elements (“steps”), each supported by a specific technique. The steps are grouped in three areas, as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Hero (values, longings, and superpower) (b) World (kingdom, inhabitants and challenge) (c) Journey (footprint, path and MTP) <p>This set of nine steps may be applied at both organizational and individual level</p>	Palao, Herrera, (2021); Charania, (2020).

Articles

Tools, schemes, instruments, steps & milestones to craft an MTP	Key Content	Sources
<i>A set of milestones</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Keeping the logic balance between the intent (“what you want to achieve”) and its appropriate wording (phrasing). 2. The formulation of the MTP for a startup is an entirely new project that starts from zero. 3. The formulation of the MTP for an existing organization requires deliberate consideration “how to elevate its current offering and strengths for a broader purpose”. 4. The officialization of the MTP should follow the testing and refinement of MTP draft(s). 5. If the MTP early version seems just as a crazy idea, it should be used as a means to pull early adopters together in small groups and ask for their intensive feedback. 6. MTP repository should be created, containing all versions of proposed MTP drafts for further review, if needed in the process of its formulation. 7. An unbiased assessment is needed whether the MTP “can draw a new community or be taken up by an existing community”. 8. The MTP “must be easy to communicate and reflect a value that resonates with others” (the constituencies). 	Palao, Lapierre, Ismail (2019)

The analysis, embedded in other tools, is determined at organizational level. Minority of these tools are officially claimed to be designed for use at both individual and team/organizational level.

Leadership stream to exploring the meaning of the MTP may also be established, encompassing two perspectives. The first perspective defines the MTP as a “highly aspirational tagline”, applied by the succeeding exponential leaders in business organizations as (Singularity University, 2018a):

- An effective means of powering a desired moonshot in an effort to realize a challenging and innovative project or undertaking with an expected deliverable as a new product or service. Under these circumstances the organizational leaders habitually prioritize radical ideas, great issues to be solved, and 10x bigger impact in comparison to the competitors.

- A landmark in the tedious process of overcoming numerous pending obstacles while attracting the best necessary talent for the respective entity.

Dissolving the traditionally assumed sharp contradiction between leaders’ aspirations of increasing the operational excellence versus promoting business innovations for radical changes by design and implementation of MTPs (Balanagarajan, Kabaly, 2018) may be pinpointed as the second perspective within the currently presented and analyzed stream in identifying important shades of meaning for the MTP construct. The aforementioned leadership aspirations are no more categorized as alternatives, and viewed as complementary ones in the pursuit of leadership endeavors for 10x business growth and potential global impact by the respective company, community and/or social movement. Through these lens

the MTP may acquire two new facets in its meaning (Balanagarajan, Kabaly, 2018):

- A qualitative measure of the lower limit of “unnecessary risk-taking” and
- A means of “promoting operational excellence”.

The outlined new streams in elaborating the meaning of the MTP may be logically arranged as a set by a useful mind-map (figure 2), categorizing the items as streams, perspectives within them, and especially culture-related perspectives. On this basis it may be concluded that the cultural facet is embedded in the MTP through:

- Its determination as an official corporate culture document
- the framework of hybrid thinking
- Its adoption as a cultural attribute, serving as a prerequisite for the establishment or joining of certain infrastructure, meant to ensure and sustain the efficient and effective interaction and alignment among necessary components inside and outside the contemporary exponential organizational setting
- Its establishment as a feature in a cherished organizational culture that should be diligently enforced by means of training and development activities

Figure 2: New streams in elaborating the meaning of the MTP

Articles

- Strongly attaching the MTP to the aggregate of official corporate culture documents by comparing it to a wider number of its items. The MTP is positioned as a substitute to traditional document of organizational purpose, i.e. the startups may design and implement only an MTP without reflecting on purpose while the existing companies, pursuing leadership through exponential growth should replace their purpose with an MTP.
- Its design and implementation by organizational leaders. Organizational leadership is always associated with solving of identified potential or pending organizational issues, and creating and changing cultures in relation to these issues.

Conclusion

The analyzed construct of the MTP has been acquiring various nuances in its meaning since its emergence in order to enable organizational leadership to deliberately pursue through their business activities simultaneously a great impact, deep changes, radical (disruptive) innovations, and 10x growth. Its formulation and implementation process depends on leadership efforts in creativity inspiration, employee engagement, organizational learning and incessant organizational renewal, balancing the interests and creating value added for a diverse and augmented number of organizational constituencies. The core shades of meaning of the MTP are outlined through the identification of two main nuances, supported by sixteen perspectives, and five of the last seem to be culture related. The set of the new streams in elaborating the meaning of the MTP consists in six items, supported by 12 perspectives, seven of which are assessed to be culture related. The possibilities of

performing and justifying numerous iterations during the design process of the MTP, and changing an already chosen MTP, position it as a prerequisite for the achievement and maintenance of organizational adaptability, agility and resilience, needed under the conditions of the VUCA business environment. The cherished organizational movement on the continuum “business related issues – undertaken/ pending change – effective and efficient leadership interventions” is initiated with the design of an MTP and is always associated with a certain cultural context (desired state of being, dominating attitudes of constituencies, e.g. resistance, collaboration, behavioral nuances in-between two extreme positions). For this reason the cultural point of view seems very important to the elucidation of the MTP construct that may be performed, grounded on the introduced categorization of its facets as these, constituting its core and those, encompassing the new identifiable streams of elaboration. That is why it should be determined as an element of proclaimed corporate culture, applied by senior leaders in business organizations to express in public their strategic intentions of developing the respective entities in the future. On this basis two new definitions for the MTP are proposed, as follows:

- (*The core of the MTP*) The MTP may be defined as a written (official) company document, intended to serve as a means of leaders’ (and sometimes constituencies’) discussing and reaching consensus around important characteristics of cherished dominating organizational culture or at least streamlining a certain cultural movement to generate great impact inside and outside the organizational setting that pursues exponential growth and competitive advantage (through talent,

Articles

communities, etc.) while maintaining the high focus of organizational leadership in the VUCA business environment.

- *(Based on the new streams)* The MTP may be defined as a project deliverable – an official corporate culture document which is designed and implemented by organizational leaders in order to realize their proactive and sometimes reactive, deep-change, and high-impact oriented interventions, based on principles of biomimicry, design thinking, management of agile and exponential organizations, pursuing both operational excellence and business innovations. The MTP comes into being within the organizational leadership context, determined by neuroscience, systems thinking and complex adaptive systems. Its design and implementation process should be taught to the personnel members, and especially the new incumbents, as the appropriate way to think, perceive and perform in relation to coping with great pending organizational issues.

Acknowledgements

This publication is funded by the UNWE Research Programme (Research Grant No. 02/2021).

References

Balanagarajan, K. B., Kabaly, P., 2018. Exponential Organization: Paytm – A Review, *Global Journal of Enterprise Information System*, Volume-10, Issue-3, July-Sep, pp34-40, section: Case Study Based Papers (CSBP), available at: <https://www.gjeis.com/index.php/GJEIS/article/view/248>, published: 2019-12-17, accessed on: 31.07.2021, EBSCO.

Berman, A., 2016a. A checklist for writing your own MTP (The most important attributes of a massive transformative purpose), available at:

<https://singularityhub.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/MTP-downloadable-2-v3.pdf>, In *The Motivating Power of a Massive Transformative Purpose*, SingularityHub, section: In focus, Nov 08, available at: <https://singularityhub.com/2016/11/08/the-motivating-power-of-a-massive-transformative-purpose/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

Berman, A., 2016b. *The Motivating Power of a Massive Transformative Purpose*, SingularityHub, section: In focus, Nov 08, available at: <https://singularityhub.com/2016/11/08/the-motivating-power-of-a-massive-transformative-purpose/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

Beveridge, D., 2015. Stand for something, *Supply House Times*, section: Innovation Strategies, 28 February, available at: <https://www.supplyht.com/articles/98395-stand-for-something>, EBSCO, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

Blank, S., 2014. Why Companies are Not Startups, March 4th, Blog post, available at: <https://steveblank.com/2014/03/04/why-companies-are-not-startups/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

Buzan, T., 2018. *Mind Map Mastery: The Complete Guide to Learning and Using the Most Powerful Thinking Tool in the Universe*, Watkins Publishing.

Calvo, J., 2020. *Journey of the Future Enterprise: How to Compete in the Age of Moonshot Leadership and Exponential Organizations*, 1st edition, Libros de Cabecera.

Charania, N., 2020. How to Find a massive transformative purpose for you and your organization, Apr 14, *Forbes*, available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesbusinesscouncil/2020/04/14/how-to-find-a-massive-transformative-purpose-for-you-and-your-organization/?sh%E2%80%A6>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

Chris, A., 2021. Top 10 search engines in the world (2021 update), June 9th, *Digital*

Articles

- marketing, available at: <https://www.reliablesoft.net/top-10-search-engines-in-the-world/>, accessed on: 30.06.2021.
- Comeaux, A., 2020. Change (the) Management: Why We as Leaders Must Change for the Change to Last, Lioncrest Publishing.
- Denison, D., Hooijberg, R., Lane, N., Lief, C., 2012. Leading Culture Change in Global Organizations: Aligning Culture and Strategy, 1st edition, San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Diamandis, P., Kotler, S., 2015. Bold. How to go big, create wealth and impact the world, New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Diamandis, P., Kotler, S., 2012. Abundance: The Future Is Better Than You Think. Free Press.
- Dimitrov, K., 2017. The aggregate of professed firm culture elements, Vanguard Scientific Instruments in Management journal (VSIM), vol.13, issue 1, 20 pages, ISSN 1314-0582, published on 5th of October 2020, available at: <https://www.vsim-journal.info/index.php?journal=vsim&page=article&op=view&path%5B%5D=160&path%5B%5D=144>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Dimitrov, K., 2016. Exploring the nuances in the relationship “culture-strategy” for the business world, “Vanguard scientific instruments in management” journal (VSIM), Volume 12, 38 pages, available at: <http://www.vsim-journal.info/index.php?journal=vsim&page=article&op=view&path%5B%5D=133&path%5B%5D=Dimitrov-2016-1>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Dimitrov, K., 2012. Critical review of models, containing cultural levels beyond the organizational one, *Economic Alternatives Journal*, Issue 1, pp.98-125, available at: https://www.unwe.bg/uploads/Alternatives/BROI_1_ALTERNATIVI_ENGLISH_2012-Kiril.pdf, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Fernandes, S., Lucas, J., Madeira, M., Cruchinho, A., 2019. Exponential System Strategy for Sustainability in Fashion Design, *Procedia CIRP*, Volume 84, pp 447-450, available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212827119309308>, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2019.04.283>
- George, B., 2017. VUCA 2.0: a strategy for steady leadership in an unsteady world, *Forbes Magazine* (with HBS Working Knowledge), published 17 February, available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/hbsworkingknowledge/2017/02/17/vuca-2-0-a-strategy-for-steady-leadership-in-an-unsteady-world/?sh=24cbbaa213d8>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Gibbons, P., 2019a. The Science of Organizational Change: How Leaders Set Strategy, Change Behavior, and Create an Agile Culture, Book 1 in series: Leading Change in the Digital Age, 2d edition, Phronesis Media.
- Gibbons, P., 2019b. IMPACT: 21st Century Change Management, Behavioral Science, Digital Transformation, and the Future of Work, Book 2 in series: Leading Change in the Digital Age, Phronesis Media.
- Goethals, G., Sorenson, G., Burns, J., 2004. Encyclopedia of leadership, p.856, Berkshire Publishing Group LLC, Sage Publications, Inc.
- Grover, V., Kettinger, W. (editors), 1998. Business Process Change: Reengineering Concepts, Methods and Technologies, Idea Group Publishing.
- Growth Institute, n.d. Massive Transformative Purpose tool, available at: https://info.growthinstitute.com/mtp-tool?utm_source=blog&utm_medium=banner&utm_campaign=t47_EXO_big_lead_MTP_10052018, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Gümüşay, A. A., 2019. Embracing Religions in Moral Theories of Leadership. *Academy of Management Perspectives* (AMP), 33, 292–306, <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2017.0130>

- Halkias, D., Santora, J., Harkiolakis, N., Thurman, P. (editors), 2020. *Leadership and Change Management: A Cross-Cultural Perspective*, Routledge.
- Hammer, M., Champy, J., 1993. *Reengineering the Corporation: A Manifesto for Business Revolution*, New York: Harper Business.
- Hiatt, J., Creasey, T., 2013. *Change Management: The People Side of Change*, Prosci Learning Center Publications.
- Innov8rs team, 2018. Exponential Growth? Start With A Massive Transformative Purpose, Innov8rs, November 25th, section: News, available at: <https://innov8rs.co/news/exponential-growth-start-with-a-massive-transformative-purpose/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Ismail, S., 2018. Massive Transformative Purpose — TheHeartbeat of Every ExO, Medium, June 11th, available at: <https://medium.com/@salimismail/massive-transformative-purpose-the-heartbeat-of-every-exo-8f59e7a811b4>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Ismail, S., Malone, M., van Geest, Y., Diamandis, P., 2014. *Exponential organizations. Why new organizations are ten times better, faster, and cheaper than yours (and what to do about it)*, New York: Diversion books.
- Jain, N., Schroeter, J., Branson, R., 2018. *Moonshots. Creating a world of abundance*, Moonshots Press™, an imprint of John August Media, LLC.
- Janicijevic, N., 2011. Methodological approaches in the research of organizational culture, *Economic annals*, Volume LVI, No. 189, April – June, pp69-99, available at: <http://www.doiserbia.nb.rs/img/doi/0013-3264/2011/0013-32641189069J.pdf>, DOI:10.2298/EKA1189069J
- Jeffery, J., 2019. What Is An Exponential Organization?, *Entrepreneur Europe*, section: Growth strategies, October 29th, available at: <https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/341439>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Kachel, U. E., Jennings, G., 2020. “A reflection on using mind maps as a tool for grounded theory analysis”, *Travel and Tourism Research Association: Advancing Tourism Research Globally*, 69, 10 pages, University of Massachusetts Amherst, ScholarWorks@UMass Amherst, available at: <https://scholarworks.umass.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2571&context=ttra>, accessed on: 15.09.2021.
- Kinkade, S., 2018. An MTP For Your ExO? Wait ... What?, *ThinkBigger*, section: Web Exclusives, July 5th, available at: <https://ithinkbigger.com/massive-transformative-purpose-for-exponential-organization/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Kok, J., van den Heuvel, S. (editors), 2019. *Leading in a VUCA World: Integrating Leadership, Discernment and Spirituality*, Springer Open.
- Lane, G., 2013. *Culturally On Plan: A Pragmatic Guide for Aligning Organizational Culture with a Strategic Plan and Transforming Management to Leadership*, Strategic-Leaders.com
- Mack, O., Khare, A., Kramer, A., Burgartz, Th. (Eds.), 2016. *Managing in a VUCA World*, Springer.
- Mayer, C., 2016. Sustaining innovation in the midst of success, *Journal of Leadership Studies*, Volume 10, Number 1, pp.73-75, Wiley Online Library, School of Advanced Studies of the University of Phoenix, EBSCO, DOI: 10.1002/jls
- Nwatarali, G., 2021. Massive Transformative Purpose: This Idea Can Change Everything, *Tech Help Canada*, May 3, available at: <https://techhelp.ca/massive-transformative-purpose/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Palao, F., Herrera, A. M., 2021. *Massive Transformative Purpose: The guide to provide*

Articles

- sense to your projects and your life, Editorial Bubok Publishing.
- Palao, F., 2020. The Purpose Launchpad Guide, July, available at: <https://www.purposelaunchpad.com/>, accessed on: 08.07.2021.
- Palao, F., 2019. Exponential Organisations: helping students to build the businesses of the future, EFMD Global Focus, Issue 1, Vol. 13, pp.29-31, available at: www.globalfocusmagazine.com, accessed on: 31.07.2021, EBSCO.
- Palao, F., LaPierre, M., Ismail, S., 2019. Exponential transformations. Evolve your organization (and change the world) with a 10-week ExO Sprint, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey.
- Palao, F., LaPierre, M., Ismail, S., Poyatos, F., Diamandis, P., 2018. Exponential transformation: the ExO Sprint playbook to evolve your organization to navigate industry disruption and change the world for the better, 1st edition, New York: Diversion Books.
- Palao, F., n.d. The best way to evolve an organization is transforming its people, O*Blog post, available at: <https://franciscopalao.com/blog/the-best-way-to-evolve-an-organization-is-transforming-its-people>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Pechstein, A., 2020. 10x your Crisis Response & Adapt to Disruption Faster, LinkedIn, March 24, available at: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/10x-your-crisis-response-adapt-disruption-faster-dr-arndt-pechstein>, accessed on: 19.05.2021.
- Peppler, L., 2019. Do you have an MTP? Your first step to exponential growth, OpenExO blog, November 04th, available at: <https://blog.openexo.com/do-you-have-an-mtp>, accessed on; 31.07.2021.
- Perez, M., n.d. A powerful exercise to help you define your massively transformative purpose(s) (mtp) and start your journey as a purpose driven leader, EmpowerGaia, available at: <https://www.empowergaia.org/how-to-define-your-purpose/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Schein, E., 1990. Organizational culture. *American Psychologist*, February, vol.45, issue 2, pp109–119.
- Schein, E., Schein, P., 2017. Organizational culture and leadership, 5th edition, Hoboken, New Jersey, Wiley.
- Singularity University, 2021. Leadership. Meet our founders, executives, and board members, section: About, available at: <https://su.org/about/leadership/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Singularity University, 2019. The Exponential Leader's Guide to Enabling Exponential Teams. A Practical Guide to Creating a Culture of Experimentation, Innovation, and 10x Growth, available at: <https://su.org/resources/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Singularity University, 2018a. The Exponential Leader's Guide to Achieving 10x Growth (by Taking Moonshots and Creating Abundance), 18th of May, p.7, available at: <https://su.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Singularity-University-SU-EB-Exponential-Leaders-Guide-to-10x-Growth-EN.pdf>, accessed on: 30.07.2021.
- Singularity University, 2018b. The exponential leadership study tour, 17th -20th of June, p.3, available at: https://lawrenceandco.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/The-Exponential-Leadership-SS_-Brochure_2018_v5-1.pdf, accessed on: 31.07.2021.
- Singularity University, n.d. An Exponential Primer: Your guide to our essential concepts, available at: <https://su.org/concepts/>, accessed on; 31.07.2021.
- SMExO community, n.d. Massively Transformative Purpose (MTP), available at: [343](https://usercontent.one/wp/www.smexo.dk/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/Abundance-</p></div><div data-bbox=)

digital-massive-transformative-purpose.pdf, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

Tattersall, C., Watts, A., Vernon, S., 2007. Mind mapping as a tool in qualitative research, 26th of June, Vol: 103, Issue: 26, pp.32-33, available at: <https://www.nursingtimes.net/archive/mind-mapping-as-a-tool-in-qualitative-research-26-06-2007/>, accessed on: 25.09.2021.

Trodden, J., n.d. Why your business needs a massive transformative purpose, available at: <https://josephtrodden.com/why-your-business-needs-a-massive-transformative-purpose/>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

Tulder, R., Verbeke, A., Jankowska, B. (Eds.), 2019. International Business in a VUCA World: the Changing Role of States and Firms, vol. 14, Book series: Progress in International Business Research, Emerald Publishing Limited.

Wheeldon, J., Ahlberg, M., 2019. Mind Maps in Qualitative Research. In: Liamputtong P. (eds) Handbook of Research Methods in Health Social Sciences. Springer, Singapore. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-5251-4_7

Wheeldon, J., Åhlberg, M. K., 2012. From the ground up: using mind maps in qualitative research. In Visualizing social science research: Maps, methods, & meaning (pp. 79-112). SAGE Publications, Inc., <https://www.doi.org/10.4135/9781483384528>

Wheeldon, J., Faubert, J., 2009. Framing Experience: Concept Maps, Mind Maps, and

Data Collection in Qualitative Research. International Journal of Qualitative Methods, 8, 68 – 83, Sage Journals, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940690900800307>

***, 2021a. The corporate website of Tesla, section: About Tesla, available at: <https://www.tesla.com/about>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

***, 2021b. Xprize – a global future positive movement, available at: www.xprize.org, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

***, 2021c. HeroX – crowdsourcing platform for enterprises and innovators, available at: <https://www.herox.com>, accessed on: 31.07.2021.

***, 2021d. Scopus, available at: <https://www.scopus.com/home.uri>

***, 2021e. EBSCO Host Web, available at: <http://search.ebscohost.com/>

***, 2021f. Emerald, available at: <http://www.emeraldinsight.com/>

***, 2021g. DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals), available at: <https://doaj.org/>

***, 2021h. Google Scholar, available at: <http://scholar.google.bg/>

***, 2021i. Ideas: Economics and Finance Research – RePEc, available at: <https://ideas.repec.org/>

***, 2021j. SSRN (Social Science Research Network), available at: <http://www.ssrn.com/en/>